

Preparation of some Unsaturated *trans*-(*E*)-Sulphide-Sulphones and Disulphones

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A stereospecifically prepared (*E*)-1-chloro-2-*p*-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbene on reaction with various sodium thiolates gave *E*-unsaturated sulphide-sulphones (2a-e) which on oxidation yielded the corresponding disulphones (3a-e). The *trans* configuration of 1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylsulphonyl)stilbene (3c) was confirmed by two more methods of preparation. The uv and ir spectral data of all the compounds have been recorded.

BIS(arylthio)ethylenes¹, vinylene sulphonyl compounds² and a number of bis(organosulphonyl) ethylenes³⁻⁶ have been reported as effective seed protectors. Recently we have reported the synthesis and structural studies of a series of unsaturated sulphide-sulphones and disulphones⁵⁻⁸. With a view that the introduction of chlorine atom may increase the activity of a sulphide-sulphone or disulphone, the preparation of the present compounds have been undertaken.

(*E*)-1-Chloro-2-*p*-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbene (1) has been prepared⁹ by oxidising the product obtained by the reaction of *p*-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride with diphenylacetylene in presence of glacial acetic acid. Compound 1 on treatment with different thiolates in absolute ethanol resulted in the formation of unsaturated sulphide-sulphones⁵⁻⁷. As it has been confirmed that the nucleophilic substitution of activated halogeno-ethylenes occurs with the retention of configuration¹⁰⁻¹⁶, these sulphide-sulphones may be considered to have been retaining the original configuration of the starting material (1). These unsaturated sulphide-sulphones (2a-e) on oxidation yielded the corresponding unsaturated *E*-disulphones (3a-e) as shown in Scheme 1.

The *trans*-configuration of (*E*)-1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylsulphonyl)stilbene (3c) has been confirmed by preparing it by two more methods.

Method 1

Capozzi *et al.*¹⁷ prepared 4, and the corresponding *para*-bromo¹⁸ and *para*-methyl⁵ substituted compounds have been reported by other workers and showed them to possess the *trans*-(*E*)-configuration. Hence, the unsaturated disulphone (3c) should be a *trans* isomer.

Method 2

(*E*)-1-*p*-Chlorophenylthiostilbene (5) obtained by the procedure of Naidu and Peeran⁵ on treatment with *p*-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride gave a compound which was found to be identical with 4 reported in method 1. This was oxidised to yield (*E*)-1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylsulphonyl)stilbene (3c). Preparation by all the three different routes yielded the same, *E*-isomer (3c). This confirms that all the other compounds reported in the present communication are also *E*-isomers.

spectra were taken in 95% ethanol with a Toshniwal spectrophotometer and ir spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-18 spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. The purity of the compounds was ascertained by tlc using silica gel G as the stationary phase and CHCl_3 -EtOAc (95 : 5) as mobile phase.

Diphenylacetylene (m.p. 60–61°)¹⁹ and *p*-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride (b.p. 86–90/5 mm)²⁰ were prepared as described.

(*E*)-1-*p*-Chlorophenylthiostilbene (5; Diphenylacetylene (17.8 g, 100 mmol) in warm light petroleum (200 ml) was treated with *p*-chlorothiophenol (14.46 g, 100 mol), and the mixture was boiled for 5 min and left overnight at room temperature. The solution was washed with 2% NaOH and water successively and dried over CaCl_2 . The residue left after evaporation of the solvent was subjected to distillation under reduced pressure. The distillate collected at 114–117°/3 mm, yielded unreacted diphenylacetylene (4.3 g). The residual viscous oil (20 g, 61.8%) solidified on treatment with methanol and melted at 73–75°. Rectystallisation of it from 95% ethanol thrice yielded colourless crystals of (*E*)-1-*p*-chlorophenylthiostilbene, m.p. 76–77° (Found: C, 74.03; H, 4.73. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$ calcd. for: C, 74.18; H, 4.67%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 286. (ϵ 20 960), 263 (23 260) and 229 nm (31 950);

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF UNSATURATED SULPHIDE-SULPHONES AND DISULPHONES

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.* °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ν_{max} (cm^{-1})		Uv, nm 95% ethanol	
				C	H	SO_2	S-aryl	λ_{max}	(ϵ_{max})
Sulphide-sulphones									
2a	71 ^a	200-202	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{19}\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	67.41 (67.47)	4.23 (4.14)	1 325, 1 150	1 085	286	(4 660)
2b	65 ^a	195-197	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	67.99 (67.98)	4.44 (4.44)	1 328, 1 150	1 085	290	(15 310)
2c	75 ^a	197-198	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{18}\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$	62.71 (62.77)	3.69 (3.65)	1 325, 1 150	1 085	290 264 233	(17 550), (16 220), (41 270)
2d	79 ^b	228-229	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	67.99 (67.98)	4.41 (4.44)	1 320, 1 145	1 085	295	(13 490)
2e	68 ^c	150-151	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	63.26 (63.69)	4.76 (4.62)	1 320, 1 145	1 080	295	(16 030)
Disulphones									
3a	72 ^d	240-241	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{19}\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	63.23 (63.10)	3.86 (3.87)	1 325, 1 145	1 075	—	
3b	78 ^d	269-271	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	63.49 (63.71)	4.18 (4.16)	1 320, 1 140	1 075	240	(15 910)
3c	97 ^d	284-285	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{18}\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	59.20 (58.99)	3.39 (3.42)	1 320, 1 155	1 080	250	(4 522)
3d	70 ^a	227-228	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	63.53 (63.71)	4.21 (4.16)	1 330, 1 150	1 085	220	(38 070)
3e	80 ^b	220-221	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	58.93 (59.13)	4.26 (4.29)	1 325, 1 145	1 080	242	(17 720)

*Recrystallised from : ^aethanol, ^bmethanol, ^cpropan-2-ol, ^dglacial acetic acid.

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. The elemental analyses were performed by Dr. R. D. MacDonald, Australian Microanalytical Service. Uv

ν_{max} (KBr) 3 050, 1 480, 1 465, 1 440, 1 085s (S-aryl), 865, 820 and 685 cm^{-1} .

(*E*)-1-*p*-Chloro-2-*p*-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbene (1): The reaction of *p*-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride with diphenylacetylene in glacial acetic acid

resulted in the formation of (*E*)-1-chloro-2-*p*-chlorophenylthiostilbene, m.p. 92–93° (lit.¹⁷ 94°). This compound on oxidation with H₂O₂ in the presence of glacial acetic acid yielded fine colourless needles of (*E*)-1-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbene, m.p. 171–72° (Found: C, 62.05; H, 3.69. C₂₀H₁₄Cl₂O₂S calcd. for: C, 61.72; H, 3.62%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 240 nm (ε 16 270); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 060, 1 620m (C=C), 1 570, 1 480, 1 470, 1 440, 1 320s (SO₂ assym), 1 145s (SO₂ sym) 1 085s (S-aryl), 820 and 725 cm⁻¹.

General method for the synthesis of (*E*)-1-alkylthio- or arylthio-2-*p*-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbenes (2a-e): To a solution of sodium ethoxide (5 mg-atom of sodium dissolved in 10 ml of absolute ethanol) an appropriate alkanethiol or arylthiol (5 mmol) was added. The resulting sodium thiolate was mixed with a solution of 1 (5 mmol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed. Reflux time was varied from 7–9 h in different cases. In many cases, the solution on cooling deposited the unsaturated sulphide-sulphone as a crystalline material which was recrystallised from 95% ethanol or any other appropriate solvent (Table 1).

General procedure for the oxidation of 2a-e to (*E*)-1-alkylsulphonyl- or arylsulphonyl-2-*p*-chlorophenylsulphonylstilbenes (3a-e): A solution of 2a-e (2 mmol) in acetic acid (50 ml) was mixed with an excess of 30% H₂O₂ (12 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The colourless crystals separated on cooling were collected on a Büchner funnel and recrystallised from an appropriate solvent (Table 1).

Stereospecific synthesis of (*E*)-1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylsulphonyl)stilbene by two different methods:

Method 1: (a) (*E*)-1,2-Bis(*p*-chlorophenylthio)stilbene (4): The procedure followed for the preparation of the compound was essentially that of Schonberg and Mustafa²¹. The product obtained on recrystallisation from isoamyl alcohol, gave needles of (*E*)-1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylthio)stilbene, m.p. 183–185° (lit.¹⁷ 187–188°) (b) (*E*)-1,2-bis(*p*-chlorophenylsulphonyl)stilbene (3c): The oxidation of 4 to 3c was carried out as described in the general procedure. The product obtained on recrystallisation from acetic acid yielded colourless crystals, m.p. 284–285°.

Method 2: (a) Reaction of *p*-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride with 5: To a solution of 5 (3.23 g, 10 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (150 ml) was added

p-chlorophenylsulphenyl chloride (1.79 g, 10 mmol) and refluxed for 14 h. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue on cooling deposited the product (4 g, 88%). Recrystallisation of the material from isoamyl alcohol gave colourless crystals, m.p. 184–185°. M.p. of the compound was not depressed on admixture with 4 prepared by method 1 (a). (b) Oxidation of 4 to 3c: The procedure followed was identical with the general method described earlier for oxidation. The compound obtained was recrystallised from acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 284–285°. There was no depression in m.m.p. with the compound 3c, obtained through the other methods.

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